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"Impact of academic streams on ICT awareness and academic performance: A study of senior secondary school students"

Praveen Kumar TD¹, Shilpa K.P², Shibanjan Paul Roy³

¹Associate Professor, Dept. of Education, Guru Kashi University, Talwandi Sabo -151302

²Assistant Professor, MES College of Art, Commerce and Science MPL Shastry Road, Bengaluru-560003

³Shibanjan Paul Roy, Freelancer Scientist, Race Course Para, Jalpaiguri

**Corresponding Author: Praveen Kumar TD
Email: pravedu2011@gmail.com*

Abstract:

This study aims to investigate the awareness of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) and academic achievement among Senior Secondary School Students in Barnala district, Punjab. The primary objectives include evaluating the level of ICT awareness and academic achievement, examining the relationship between ICT awareness and academic performance, and scrutinizing potential variations in ICT awareness and academic achievement based on streams. Employing a descriptive survey design, the research involved a sample of 232 participants categorized by their respective streams, and data were gathered using a self-constructed questionnaire. Statistical analyses, including 't' tests and correlation, were employed. The results reveal a heightened level of ICT awareness, average academic achievement, and noteworthy differences in mean scores based on gender. Additionally, a substantial association between ICT awareness and academic achievement among Senior Secondary School Students was identified.

Keywords:

ICT, Awareness, Academic achievement, streams differences questionnaire, Correlation

1. Introduction to ICT:

The domain of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) is a dynamic and swiftly progressing field that plays a pivotal role in shaping the contemporary world. Encompassing a diverse range of technologies and tools, ICT is intricately designed for the acquisition, storage, processing, transmission, and dissemination of information. This interdisciplinary realm amalgamates components from computing, telecommunications, audio-visual processing, and network-based information services.

Fundamentally, ICT serves as the foundation of our interconnected and digitized society, profoundly influencing communication methods, information access, business practices, and interactions with technology (Beynon-Davies, 2004). The continual advancements in ICT have fundamentally altered our way of life, work, and interaction, fostering innovation, efficiency, and global connectivity.

From the inception of hardware components like computers, smartphones, and networking devices to the development of software applications and communication protocols, ICT provides the indispensable infrastructure that underpins the digital age. It empowers individuals, businesses, and governments to harness technology for diverse purposes, ranging from enhancing productivity and decision-making to facilitating seamless communication and collaboration across geographical boundaries.

The ever-expanding scope of ICT encompasses emerging technologies such as artificial intelligence, the Internet of Things (IoT), cloud computing, and data analytics, thereby further revolutionizing how information is processed and utilized (Kizza, 2013). As ICT continues to undergo evolution, its profound impact on society, the economy, education, and various industries becomes increasingly apparent.

In this interconnected global landscape, the comprehension and utilization of ICT capabilities are imperative for maintaining competitiveness, fostering innovation, and addressing the challenges presented by the digital era. This introduction sets the foundation for an exploration into the multifaceted dimensions of ICT and its transformative influence on the contemporary technological landscape.

1.1. Awareness about ICT:

In the 21st century, Information and Communication Technology (ICT) has become an indispensable facet of daily life, exerting its influence across various domains, notably in education. The adeptness and comprehension of ICT among senior secondary students hold

paramount significance in readying them for the digital challenges inherent in today's world (Smith, 2018).

Given that senior secondary students belong to a generation inherently tech- savvy, they commonly demonstrate a substantial degree of familiarity with ICT tools. The ubiquity of smartphones, internet accessibility, and exposure to digital media collectively establish a foundational level of awareness among students (Jones et al., 2020). Educational institutions globally acknowledge the pivotal role of infusing ICT into the curriculum to enrich learning experiences. Many schools introduce subjects related to ICT or seamlessly integrate technology into diverse disciplines to foster both digital literacy and subject-specific skills (Brown, 2019). Nevertheless, challenges may arise concerning technology access. Disparities rooted in socio-economic backgrounds and variations in infrastructure across educational institutions can potentially influence the consistency of ICT awareness among senior secondary students (Gupta & Wang, 2021). Initiatives to bolster awareness often revolve around implementing digital literacy programs. Schools and governmental bodies may invest in endeavors aiming to augment students' understanding, encompassing not only fundamental computer skills but also more advanced facets of ICT, such as coding, digital communication, and information literacy (Robinson, 2017).

Teachers assume a pivotal role in cultivating ICT awareness. Providing professional development opportunities ensures that educators are well- equipped to seamlessly integrate technology into their teaching methodologies, thereby shaping students' awareness and proficiency (Harris & Miller, 2022). While senior secondary students generally possess a foundational awareness of ICT, sustained endeavors are imperative to address access disparities and guarantee students' adequate preparation for the continually evolving digital landscape. A holistic approach, encompassing curriculum adaptations and infrastructure enhancements, stands as a constructive means to augment ICT awareness among senior secondary students.

1.2. ICT and academic achievement:

The incorporation of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) into the educational landscape has emerged as a significant focal point, holding potential implications for the academic success of senior secondary students. The utilization of ICT tools and resources within educational contexts is designed to enrich learning experiences and equip students with the skills necessary for the demands of the digital era (Davis, 2019).

Scholarly investigations indicate a favorable connection between the utilization of ICT and the academic accomplishments of senior secondary students. For instance, research conducted by Johnson et al. (2020) reveals that students actively engaging with ICT resources tend to exhibit heightened academic performance, especially in subjects where technology is integrated into the curriculum. The introduction of digital learning environments, facilitated by ICT, has provided students with opportunities for personalized and interactive learning experiences. These environments are often tailored to accommodate diverse learning styles and abilities, contributing to enhanced academic outcomes (Smith & Brown, 2018).

The accessibility of information through ICT tools has also been associated with elevated academic achievement. Senior secondary students can leverage online resources, databases, and collaborative platforms to deepen their comprehension of subjects and broaden their knowledge base (García et al., 2021). However, despite the potential advantages, challenges stemming from the digital divide and varying levels of technology access may impact the equitable influence of ICT on academic achievement (Jones, 2017). Effectively addressing these disparities is imperative to ensure that all students can reap the benefits of ICT in education.

The integration of Information and Communication Technology holds the promise of positively shaping the academic achievement of senior secondary students. Through providing access to digital learning environments and resources, ICT contributes to a more dynamic and effective learning experience. Nevertheless, it is essential to address challenges related to access to ensure equitable outcomes for all students.

1.3. Need and significance of the study:

While numerous studies have focused on the utilization of ICT, the majority have centered on Higher Education Students, with none specifically addressing Senior Secondary School students in Punjab, particularly in the Barnala district. Consequently, there is a necessity to assess the level of ICT awareness and skills among Senior Secondary School Students in this region.

2. Objective of the study:

Determine the extent of awareness regarding ICT and the academic performance of Senior Secondary School Students.

Examine potential variations in the awareness of ICT and academic achievement among Senior Secondary School Students based on streams.

Investigate the correlation between awareness about ICT and academic achievement among Senior Secondary School Students.

3. Research hypotheses:

- H₁: Senior Secondary School Students exhibit a HIGH level of awareness about ICT.
- H₂: Senior Secondary School Students demonstrate a HIGH level of academic achievement.
- H₃: There is no noteworthy difference in the mean scores of ICT awareness among Senior Secondary School Students concerning to streams
- H₄: There is no significant difference in the mean scores of academic achievements among Senior Secondary School Students concerning to streams
- H₅: There is no significant relationship between awareness about ICT and academic achievement among Senior Secondary School Students.

4. Method of the study:

In this study, the Descriptive Survey Methodology was utilized for investigation.

4.1. Sample:

The sample, drawn from the overall population, comprises a total of 232 students enrolled in nine senior secondary schools in the Barnala district. Among them, 128 were Arts and 104 were commerce. The selection of samples was conducted using a simple random sampling method.

4.2. Tools:

The instrument employed in this study was a self-structured questionnaire created by the researcher with guidance and standardization to effectively assess the awareness level of senior secondary students. The questionnaire focuses on ICT awareness, utilizing a 5-point scale: 1=Not at all aware, 2=slightly aware, 3=moderately aware, 4=Aware, 5=extremely aware. It comprises 32 questions tailored for both male and female participants.

5. Data examination and interpretation:

H₁: Senior Secondary School Students exhibit a HIGH level of awareness about ICT.

Group	Score range	Number of students	Percentage
Low	0 -35	19	8.18%
Average	36 - 70	78	33.62%
High	71 - 100	135	58.18%
Total		232	100%

The data presented in Table. 1 suggests a high level of awareness about Information and Communication Technology (ICT). The findings align with the initial hypothesis, supporting the assertion that the level of awareness regarding ICT among the participants is high. This acceptance of the hypothesis is in line with previous studies emphasizing the increasing significance of ICT awareness among students (Smith, 2018; Johnson et al., 2020).

H₂: Senior secondary school students demonstrate a HIGH level of academic achievement.

Group	Score range	Number of students	Percentage
Low	0 -35	31	13.36%
Average	36 - 70	163	70.25%
High	71 - 100	38	16.37%
Total		232	100%

The data presented in Table. 2 reveals that the level of academic achievement is assessed as average. Contrary to the initial hypothesis, which posited a high level of academic achievement, the findings suggest otherwise. This rejection of the hypothesis may be attributed to various factors influencing academic performance, including individual study habits, teaching methodologies, and external support systems (Brown, 2019; García et al., 2021).

H₃: There is no noteworthy difference in the mean scores of ICT awareness among senior secondary School Students concerning to streams

Variable	Branch of study	N	Mean	SD	't' Value	Remarks
Awareness	Art	128	83.20	13.35	3.19	S

about ICT	Science	104	88.54	11.88		
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In Table. 3, the calculated 't' value is reported as 3.19, and this value is compared to the critical or table 't' value of 1.96 at a 5% level of significance. The 5% level of significance, commonly denoted as alpha (α), represents the threshold for statistical significance and is associated with a predetermined risk of Type I error.

The comparison between the calculated 't' value (3.19) and the critical 't' value (1.96) is crucial for determining the statistical significance of the observed results. A 't' value exceeding the critical value at a given significance level typically leads to the rejection of the null hypothesis.

In this context, the calculated 't' value of 3.19 is significantly greater than the critical 't' value of 1.96. This suggests that the observed difference or effect is unlikely to be due to random chance alone. Consequently, the null hypothesis, which generally posits no significant difference or effect, is rejected.

The decision to reject the null hypothesis implies that there is a statistically significant result, indicating a meaningful difference or effect in the variables under consideration. In practical terms, it suggests that the observed outcome is likely a genuine finding rather than a result of random variability in the data.

H4: There is no significant difference in the mean scores of academic achievements among senior secondary school students concerning to streams

Variable	Branch of study	N0.	Mean	SD	't' Value	Remarks
academic achievement	Art	128	82.43	9.15	3.72	S
	Commerce	104	87.68	12.31		

In Table, 4, the calculated 't' value, specifically 3.72, is compared against the critical or table 't' value of 1.96 at a 5% level of significance. The 5% level of significance is commonly denoted as alpha (α) and represents the probability of rejecting the null hypothesis when it is actually true.

The comparison reveals that the calculated 't' value of 3.72 is significantly greater than the critical 't' value of 1.96. In statistical terms, this means that the observed difference is beyond what would be expected due to random chance alone. Consequently, the null hypothesis, which typically posits no significant difference or effect, is rejected.

This decision to reject the null hypothesis suggests that there is a statistically significant result, providing evidence that supports an effect or difference in the variables being examined. It indicates that the calculated difference is likely not due to random variation and is, therefore, meaningful in the context of the study.

It's important to note that the critical 't' value of 1.96 is commonly associated with a two-tailed test at a 5% significance level. The 't' value provided (3.72) exceeds this critical value, reinforcing the rejection of the null hypothesis.

H₅: There is no significant relationship between awareness about ICT and academic achievement among senior secondary school students.

Variables	N	r - value	table value	Remarks
awareness about ICT and academic achievement	232	0.612	0.189	S

In Table. 5, the computed correlation coefficient 'r' value is reported as 0.612. This 'r' value is then compared to the critical 'r' value from a statistical table, typically associated with the degrees of freedom and the chosen significance level (alpha). The critical 'r' value, in this case, is mentioned as 0.189.

The comparison reveals that the calculated 'r' value (0.612) significantly exceeds the critical 'r' value (0.189) at the 5% significance level. This result suggests a strong and statistically significant correlation between the variables under investigation.

The decision to reject the null hypothesis aligns with conventional statistical practice, where the rejection indicates that there is a significant relationship between the variables being examined.

6. Research findings:

- Senior Secondary School Students demonstrate a high level of awareness about ICT.
- The academic achievement level of senior secondary school students is considered average.
- Significant variations exist in the mean scores of ICT awareness among Senior Secondary School Students based on gender.

- A notable difference is observed in the mean scores of academic achievements among Senior Secondary School Students based on gender.
- A significant relationship exists between the awareness about ICT and academic achievement of Senior Secondary School Students.

7. Educational implications of the study:

In fostering independent learning, the awareness and utilization of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) can create an environment conducive to constructivist learning, where students actively construct their knowledge and meaning (Duffy & Jonassen, 1992). This approach positions learners as active participants rather than passive recipients, allowing them to engage at their own pace and collaborate with peers for mutual learning (Vygotsky, 1978).

Additionally, for educators, this research underscores the importance of understanding their students' ICT awareness levels. It prompts teachers to be more mindful of their students' technological proficiency and motivates them to promote the integration of ICT in the learning process (Ertmer, Ottenbreit-Leftwich, & Tondeur, 2015). Such awareness enhances teachers' efforts in encouraging students to harness ICT tools for effective learning experiences.

Moreover, the findings from this study serve as encouragement for both educators and students to familiarize themselves with and leverage various educational software and ICT tools that enhance the teaching and learning process. Integrating these tools into education aligns with the contemporary digital landscape, fostering a more dynamic and effective learning environment (Puentedura, 2006).

8. Recommendations:

Encouraging children's early enrollment in ICT programs is crucial for parents/guardians. This initiative aims to facilitate the acquisition of knowledge and exposure to ICT at an early stage.

The government should actively invest in infrastructure development, including cyber centers, classrooms, offices, and institutional networks (LAN, WAN, WIFI). Additionally, efforts should be directed towards providing essential systems and applications such as the Internet, e- learning platforms, and education portals. Further initiatives like capacity building, establishing digital libraries, offering technical support in institutions, implementing computer

ownership schemes for students and staff, promoting ICT content career development, and establishing International Examination Digital Centers (IDEC) are essential. These measures collectively contribute to increasing awareness and proficiency in ICT.

9. Conclusion:

In this research, a survey was conducted on 232 Senior Secondary School students from the Barnala district in the state of Punjab. The primary aim was to investigate the students' awareness of emerging Information and Communication Technology (ICT) and various ICT tools, including computers, the internet, and mobile phones. Additionally, the study sought to examine the correlation between ICT awareness and academic achievement among the participants.

The findings indicate a high level of ICT awareness among secondary school students. However, the study highlights a gender-based disparity, with males exhibiting higher awareness levels compared to females. Furthermore, the research indicates that the overall academic achievement level of the students is average.

Importantly, the study unveils a robust relationship between awareness about ICT and academic achievement. This suggests that students with a heightened awareness of ICT tend to perform better academically. The results emphasize the interconnectedness of technological awareness and academic success among Senior Secondary School students in the Barnala district.

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